

Study of Beans of *Pithecolobium saman* Benth

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Pithecolobium saman Benth beans yielded free sucrose and a new saponin named as Samanin B which is a glycoside of Acacic acid with glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose in molar ratio of 4 : 2 : 1 : 1.

PITHECOLOBIUM *saman* commonly known as 'Raintree' is a member of family Leguminosae, sub-family Mimoseae. Nigam *et al*¹ reported a number of compounds viz. hexacosanol, octacosanol, octacosanoic acid, β -D-glucoside of α -spinasterol, α -spinasterone, hentricotane, lupeonone, lupeol, palmetic acid and stearic acid and a mixture of flavonoids including kaempferol in various parts of the plant and did not encounter any saponin in any part. The presence of saponin was reported in the bark by earlier workers². The leaves have been reported to contain alkaloids^{3,4}.

Varshney *et al*⁵ have studied the saponin samanin A of the seeds and found it to be a glycoside of acacic acid with 15 moles of four sugars.

The present investigation deals with the study of the saponin and free sugars of the beans without seeds, from which saponin and sucrose was isolated in good quantities.

The purity of saponin a colourless product, m.p. 194-196° [α]_D = -74 (C-0.98 MeOH) was tested by TLC and electrophoresis, and has been named as Samanin B. It formed an acetate, m.p. 150-152° [α]_D = -54 (C-1%CHCl₃) samanin B on acid hydrolysis with sulphuric acid in usual manner⁶ gave an acid genin (25%) identified as acacic acid (3 β , 16 β , 21 β , trihydroxy, olean-12-ene-18- α -H, 28 oic acid). Acid genin on acetylation gave acacic acid diacetyl lactone⁷. The fractions 26-35 gave crystalline compound which has been identified as sucrose.

The sugars obtained by hydrolysis of, samanin B on paper chromatography in butanol: pyridine: water (6 : 4 : 3) showed the presence of four sugars identified as glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose by co-chromatography with authentic samples. The sugars were then separated by preparative paper chromatography and were separately estimated by photocolometric method⁸ and the molar ratio of glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose was found to be 4 : 2 : 1 : 1.

Samanin B on alkaline hydrolysis with methanolic potassium hydroxide did not give any sugar and the saponin was recovered unchanged indicating the absence of ester linkage in Samanin B i.e. there are no sugars attached at C-28 COOH group.

The infra-red spectra of samanin B and its acetate did not show any lactonisation on acetylation, between 21 hydroxyl and 28 carboxylic groups as is the case of acacic acid⁷. This indicated that 21 hydroxyl group is not free in the samanin B and all the sugars are attached at all the three hydroxyl groups or any of them (C-3OH, C-16 OH, C-21 OH). All attempts to knock out the sugars selectively failed.

On the basis of the above observations, samanin B, is concluded to be a glycoside of acacic acid (3 β , 16 β , 21 β , trihydroxy-olean-12-ene, 18 α -H, 28 oic acid) with glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose present in molar ratio of 4 : 2 : 1 : 1 attached at C-3, C-16 and C-21 hydroxyl groups.

$R' + R'' + R''' = \text{Glucose} :$
Arabenose. Xylose : Rhamnose
(4 : 2 : 1 : 1)

Fig. 1

Experimental

Isolation of Sucrose and Samanin B :

The beans (500 gms) were broken and after the removal of seeds, defatted with petroleum ether (60-80°). Removal of petroleum ether yielded a dark yellow green oily substance (5.5 gms). The well defatted pieces of beans were exhaustively extracted with ethanol. Ethanolic extract was concentrated and left for several days, it gave a colourless crystalline substance m.p. 186° which has been identified as sucrose by mixed m.p. and paper chromatography with authentic sample. The filtrate was then evaporated under reduced pressure to yield a brown syrupy mass which was successively extracted with petroleum ether, ether chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and acetone⁶. The residue was dissolved in minimum quantity of methanol and precipitated by adding to a large amount of acetone/ether, to yield a light brown powder (30 gms). On TLC it showed two spots. The mixture was further purified by chromatography on column of silica gel using butanol : methanol : water (10 : 4 : 14) as eluant fractions 920 gave pure saponin, Samanin B as colourless powder. m.p. 194-196°. The purity of the saponin was confirmed by two dimensional thin layer chromatography and by electrophoresis (300 volts, borate buffer).

Acetylation of Samanin B :

Samanin B (50 mg) was suspended in pyridine (5 ml) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) was added to it. The mixture was kept over night. It was then poured over ice/water with constant stirring. After standing for half an hour it was filtered and dried. It was dissolved in chloroform and precipitated by adding dropwise to petroleum ether. It gave colourless substance, m.p. 150-152° [α]_D²⁰ = -54 (C. 1% CHCl₃).

Acid hydrolysis of Saponin :

Saponin (200 mg) was dissolved in 100 ml of water and sulphuric acid was added to make 10%, it was heated on water bath for an hour and then refluxed for 4 hr. Sapogenin which separated was filtered, washed free of acid and dried (58 mg).

Purification of the genin :

The genin (50 mg) was dissolved in 5% methanolic potassium hydroxide and refluxed for 2 hr. on water bath. Thereafter half of the methanol was evaporated and the contents were diluted with water and extracted a number of times with ether. Aqueous solution left was acidified with hydrochloric acid which precipitated genin. It was filtered, washed and dried. It was crystallised from methanol and had m.p. 275-282°. The genin was identified as acacic acid by m.p., m.m.p. and TLC with

authentic sample of acacic acid. Acetate, m.p. 235-236° crystallised from methanol, was identified with acacic acid acetate by, direct comparison with the authentic samples.

Identification of sugars :

Hydrolysate obtained by acid hydrolysis of Samanin B was neutralised with freshly precipitated barium carbonate and then deionised by passing through the columns of ion-exchange resins (Amberlite IRA 400 and Amberlite IR 120 (H⁺)). The neutral sugar solution thus obtained was evaporated under reduced pressure to yield a light brown syrup. It was then chromatographed on Whatman filter paper No-1 alongside with authentic samples of sugars, this showed the presence of 4 sugars identified as glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose.

Separation and estimation of sugars :

The sugar mixture was applied as a narrow streak on Whatman filter paper No. 3MM. After running the paper for 60 hr. in butanol : pyridine : water (6 : 4 : 3) the strips were cut by the aid of guide strips. Extraction of strips separately with 50% methanol and evaporation gave four different sugars, the purity of which was tested again by paper chromatography. The sugars were then estimated as glucose by photocolometric method using phenol sulphuric acid⁸. This gave the molar ratio of glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose as 4 : 2 : 1 : 1.

Alkaline hydrolysis of saponin :

Saponin (50 mg) was dissolved in 50 ml. of methanol and to it aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (50 ml, 5%) was added and then refluxed for 4 hr. on water bath. The methanol was slowly evaporated adding water to make up the constant volume and then neutralised with hydrochloric acid. This was then extracted with *n*-butanol. The butanol extract on evaporation to dryness under reduced pressure and paper chromatography did not reveal the presence of any sugar. On TLC, it did not show any change in mobility from the mobility of the starting material, i.e. Samanin B.

Free Sugars :

The fraction (26-36) from column chromatography gave a crystalline product which has been identified as free sucrose by m.p., m.m.p. and paper chromatography with authentic sample of sucrose.

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